

A Study to Assess the Factors Influencing Delay in Initiation of the Post-Exposure Prophylaxis among Animal Bite Victims Attending Anti-Rabies Clinic of A Tertiary Care Hospital in Southern Rajasthan under National Rabies Control Programme

Sugandha Shah¹, Bharti Paliwal², Nithya Devaraj³, Jatin Prajapati⁴, Shivani Vihan⁵

^{1,3,4,5} Resident, Department of Community Medicine, RNT Medical College, Udaipur

²Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, RNT Medical College, Udaipur

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Sugandha Shah

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Abstract:

Introduction: Rabies remains a significant public health concern, particularly in India where it is endemic and predominantly transmitted through dog bites. Despite being preventable with timely post-exposure prophylaxis (PEP), rabies claims thousands of lives annually, primarily in Asia and Africa.

Aim: This hospital-based cross-sectional study aimed to assess the delay in initiating immediate post exposure prophylaxis and investigate factors contributing to this delay among animal bite victims.

Methodology: The study was conducted at the Anti-Rabies Clinic of Maharana Bhupal Government Hospital in Udaipur, Rajasthan. A total of 126 participants were interviewed, and the data was collected using a modified predesigned questionnaire.

Results: The study revealed a demographic profile inclined towards young adults (21-30 years) and children (<10 years), with males comprising 60.32% of the sample. The dogs were the primary biting animals (69%). Notably, 57.14% of bites were categorized as severe (Category III). The study found a high prevalence (88.9%) of delayed PEP initiation (>6 hours) among participants. Factors significantly associated with delays included younger age groups and the unavailability of vaccines at hospitals. Reasons cited for delays included lack of vaccine/immunoglobulin at peripheral centres (19.64%), absence of a companion (16.96%), and inadequate awareness about rabies severity (11.61%). Work-related constraints (10.71%) and misconceptions regarding rabies transmission (3.57%) further contributed to delayed treatment.

Conclusion: These findings focus on the critical need for improved vaccine accessibility, enhanced public education on rabies prevention, and targeted interventions to address logistical barriers in both urban and rural settings. Recommendations include implementing robust education campaigns, enhancing vaccine availability at peripheral health facilities and developing policies to ensure equitable access to PEP, particularly for vulnerable populations.

Keywords: Rabies, Post Exposure Prophylaxis, Animal Bite, Delay in Seeking Treatment.

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Introduction

Rabies is a severe, often fatal viral disease affecting the central nervous system, transmitted primarily through bites or scratches from infected animals, especially dogs. Despite being preventable with timely post-exposure prophylaxis (PEP), rabies claims tens of thousands of lives annually, predominantly in Asia and Africa where awareness and access to PEP can be limited.[1] In India, where rabies is endemic, dog bites account for the vast majority of cases, highlighting the critical need for immediate medical intervention.[2] Rabies deaths in human are 100% preventable through prompt and appropriate medical care. Because of 100% fatality rate of rabies, animal bites should be considered as a “medical emergency” and the “life-

saving” post-exposure prophylaxis should be promptly provided, which is very much effective in prevention of the disease.[3] Delays in seeking PEP can compromise its effectiveness, underscoring the importance of identifying factors contributing to these delays. This study aims to investigate such factors to enhance understanding and promote timely administration of life-saving PEP, crucial in achieving the global goal of eliminating rabies deaths by 2030 through improved public awareness and healthcare delivery.

Methodology

The study was conducted as a hospital-based, cross-sectional investigation at the Anti-Rabies

Clinic of Maharana Bhupal Government Hospital in Udaipur, Rajasthan for a period of 3 months from April to June 2024. The sample size of 126 participants was determined using a formula based on a previous study's findings [4] on delays in post-exposure prophylaxis (PEP) initiation.

Non-probability convenient sampling was employed to select animal bite victims attending the clinic, specifically those categorized as II and III according to severity, and who provided consent or assent for participation. Excluded were Category I cases, individuals receiving pre-exposure prophylaxis, and severe bite cases necessitating hospitalization. Data collection involved face-to-face interviews using a semi-structured questionnaire, adapted from a pre-tested tool. Data were coded in Microsoft Excel and analysed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), employing descriptive statistics and chi-square tests for qualitative comparisons. The study adhered to ethical guidelines, with plans for approval from the Ethical Review Committee at RNT Medical College, Udaipur.

Results

During the study conducted at the Anti-Rabies Centre of Maharana Bhupal Government Hospital, 126 animal bite victims were interviewed, revealing a predominantly male (60.32%) and urban-dwelling (72.22%) demographic. The majority of

participants fell within the age group of 21-30 years (23.81%), with a significant proportion being children (20.63%) under 10 years old. (Table 1)

Dogs were the most common animals responsible for bites (69%), followed by cats (13.5%) and other wild animals (9.5%). Category III bites were prevalent among 57.14% of cases, with the lower limbs (55.56%) being the most frequently bitten site. (Table 2)

The study found a high incidence of delay (>6 hours) in initiating anti-rabies post-exposure prophylaxis (PEP), affecting 88.9% of participants, while only 11.1% received PEP on time. (Table 3) Factors significantly associated with delayed PEP initiation included younger age groups and the unavailability of vaccines at hospitals. (Table 4) Reasons cited for delays included lack of vaccine/immunoglobulin at peripheral centres (19.64%), absence of a companion to accompany victims (16.96%), and unawareness about the severity and fatality of rabies (11.61%).

Work-related hindrances (10.71%) and misconceptions regarding rabies transmission (3.57%) also contributed to delayed treatment. (Figure 1) These findings underscore the critical need for improved vaccine accessibility at healthcare facilities, enhanced public education about rabies prevention, and targeted interventions to address logistical barriers faced by urban and rural communities alike.

Table 1: Distribution of socio-demographic characteristics of animal bite victims

Socio-demographic and clinical characteristics		Number (n=126)	Percentage (%)
Age	≤ 10	26	20.63%
	11-20	20	15.87%
	21-30	30	23.81%
	31-40	20	15.87%
	41-50	6	4.76%
	50-60	8	6.35%
	>60	16	12.70%
	Total	126	100%
Gender	Female	50	39.68%
	Male	76	60.32%
	Total	126	100%
Residence	Rural	35	27.78%
	Urban	91	72.22%
	Total	126	100%
Educational Status	illiterate	15	11.90%
	Primary	39	30.95%
	Secondary	54	42.86%
	Graduate	18	14.29%
	Post-graduate	0	0.00%
	Total	126	100%
Occupation	Businessman	16	12.70%
	Government employee	5	3.97%
	Private employee	39	30.95%
	Farmer	16	12.70%
	Animal Handler	0	0%
	Housewife	14	11.11%

	Student	36	28.57%
	Retired serviceman	0	0%
	Total	126	100%
Monthly family income (INR)	<10,000	31	24.60%
	>10,000	95	75.40%
	Total	126	100%
Availability of hospital nearby (<10km)	Yes	101	80.16%
	No	25	19.84%
	Total	126	100%
Availability of anti-rabies vaccine in the hospital	Yes	16	12.7%
	No	42	33.3%
	Do not know	43	34.1%
	No hospital nearby	25	19.8%
	Total	126	100%

Table 2: Distribution of clinical characteristics of animal bite victims

Characteristics		Number	Percentage
Type of animal bite	Dog	87	69%
	Cat	17	13.5%
	Monkey	10	7.9%
	Other wild animals	12	9.5%
	Total	126	100%
Category of bite	II	54	42.86%
	III	72	57.14%
	Total	126	100%
Site of bite	Head/ neck/ trunk	5	3.97%
	Upper Limb	35	27.78%
	Lower Limb	70	55.56%
	Face	5	3.97%
	Genitals	0	0%
	Multiple sites	11	8.73%
	Total	126	100%

Table 3: Delay in initiation of PEP among animal bite victims (n=126)

Post Exposure Prophylaxis	Animal bite victim n=126 (%)
On time (<6 hours)	14 (11.1%)
Delayed	112 (88.9%)
Total	126 (100%)
Out of the total delayed: for 6-48 hour	76 (67.9%)
for >48 hours	36 (32.1%)
Total	112(100%)

Table 4: Factors associated with delay in initiation of PEP among animal bite victims

Variables	Delay in PEP			P value
	Yes n=112 (88.9%)	No n=14 (11.1%)	Total n=126 (100%)	
Age (Years)	<10	26(23.2%)	0(0%)	P value = 0.045 (significant) df= 6 Chi-square =12.895
	11-20	19 (95%)	1(5%)	
	21-30	27 (90%)	3 (10%)	
	31-40	15(75%)	5(25%)	
	41-50	4(66.6%)	2(33.4%)	
	51-60	8(100%)	0(0%)	
	>60	13(81.2%)	3(18.8%)	
	Total	112	14	
Gender	Female	47(94%)	3(6%)	P value = 0.139 df= 1 Chi-square =2.193
	Male	65(85.5%)	11(14.5%)	
	Total	112	14	

Residence	Rural	34(97.1%)	1(2.9%)	35	P value = 0.110 (Fischer's Exact Test)
	Urban	78(85.7%)	13(14.3%)	91	
	Total	112	14	126	
Availability of hospital nearby (<10km)	Yes	91(90.1%)	10(9.9%)	101	P-value = 0.6 df = 1 Chi-square = 0.26
	No	21(84%)	4(16%)	26	
	Total	112	14	126	
Availability of vaccine in the hospital	Yes	15(93.75%)	1(6.25%)	16	P-value = 0.015 (significant) df=3 Chi square value =10.435
	No	42(100%)	0(0%)	42	
	Don't know	34(79%)	9(21%)	43	
	No hospital nearby	21(84%)	4(16%)	25	
	Total	112	14	126	
Category of bite	Category II	48 (88.9%)	6 (11.11%)	54	P-value = 1 df = 1 Chi-square=0.00
	Category III	64 (88.9%)	8 (11.11%)	72	
	Total	112	14	126	

Figure 1: Reasons for delay in initiation of PEP

Discussion:

In this study involving 126 animal bite victims, the demographic profile showed a predominant involvement of young adults aged 21-30 years and children under 10 years, consistent with findings from similar studies by Surwade et al. [5] and Esmailzadeh et al. [6], where the most common age group involved was also 21-30 years (22.3%) followed by 11-20 years (19.61%) and less than 30years, respectively. Males were more frequently affected than females, aligning with previous research by Esmailzadeh et al. [6] and Surwade et al. [5], highlighting a consistent gender distribution among bite victims. Availability of hospitals within close proximity was reported by a substantial proportion of participants, similar to findings by Wani et al. [4] where, 52.5% reported nearby availability

of the hospital. Contrasting findings were reported in other studies such as Kisaka et al. [7], where 63.3% participants reported nearby hospital at the distance of more than 10 kilometres from their residence.

In the present study majority of the bite cases were from dogs (69%) followed by cat (13.5%) with bites from other wild animals accounting for 9.5% which is similar to the findings conducted by Surwade et al. [5] In the study by Khazaei et al.[8] et al domestic dogs (59.1%) most commonly involved followed by cats (20.9%) and stray dogs (10.3%). It was observed that 57.14% of the animal bites are category III bites which is similar to the findings of the studies conducted by Surwade et al.[5] In the present study the prevalence of delay in initiating post exposure prophylaxis (more than 6

hours from the time of exposure) was observed to be 88.9%. A contrast finding is observed in the study conducted by Wani et al.[4] where majority (72.36%) of the participants reported to the health facility within 6 hours of exposure and in a study by Esmailzadeh et al.[6] majority reported on time with a delay in initiating PEP reported by only 6.8% of the respondents.

A retrospective study by Patil AR et al. [9] reported a delay of only 24.9% with majority participants receiving prompt PEP in the hospitals. Findings similar to the present study is seen in a study by Khazaei et al.[8] where 62.82% participants reported a delay of more than 6 hours from exposure. Ravish HS et al. [10] reported a delay of 41.4% in Bangalore. A study by Addai JA et al. [11] reported a delay of 69.5%.

The present study showed a significant association between age of the bite victim and unavailability of the vaccine in the hospital with the delay in initiation which is a similar to a study finding conducted by Ravish HS et al. [10] which showed a significant association between age, place of residence, type of biting animal and type of exposure with delay. Joseph J, Sangeetha et al[12] showed similar result with age, distance from the vaccination centre having significant association with delay. A contrast result was noted in studies by Wani et al. [4] and Patil AR et al.[9] where age was not associated with the delay in PEP initiation instead cases from rural background tend to delay more and had a significant association in the latter study with a p value of 0.0008.

Reason for the delay in initiation of PEP cited by the study participants in the present study was lack of vaccine/immunoglobulin at the periphery (19.64%) followed by unavailability of a person to accompany (16.96%). About 11.61% of the participants were unaware about the severity/ fatality of the disease. Work related hindrance was seen in (10.71%) of the participants.

In a study by Surwade et al.[5] most common reason for delay in initiating PEP was lack of knowledge (46.15%) followed by distance from ARC (26.37%) with unavailability of vaccine in the periphery by 23.08%. Ravish HS et al.[10] reported lack of awareness about PEP (33.2%) followed by problems in transportation and access to health care facility (20.3%) as the reasons for the delay. In a study by Wani et al.[4] most common reason (31%) cited was lack of money.

In a hospital based cross sectional study conducted in Delhi, most common reasons for inability to receive prompt PEP were work (42.7%), ARC being closed on National holidays (36.6%) Joseph J, Sangeetha et al[12]

Limitations:

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The present study was conducted in a tertiary care set up and included only the ones who sought treatment at the Anti-Rabies Clinic, so it might be possible that our study would have missed animal bite cases who did not seek treatment and the results could not be generalized to the community. The study's retrospective nature might introduce recall bias, affecting the accuracy of reported delays.

Conclusion

These findings underscore the critical need for improved vaccine accessibility, enhanced public education on rabies prevention, and targeted interventions to address logistical barriers in both urban and rural settings. Recommendations include implementing robust education campaigns, enhancing vaccine availability at peripheral health facilities, engaging communities through outreach programs, optimizing hospital operations for PEP delivery, and developing policies to ensure equitable access to PEP, particularly for vulnerable populations. In conclusion, addressing these barriers is crucial to achieving the global goal of eliminating rabies deaths by 2030. Continued research and implementation of evidence-based interventions are essential to mitigate delays in PEP initiation and improve outcomes for animal bite victims.

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